

Analysis of the Teacher's Preparation for the Lesson (In the Case of Foreign Languages)

Ra'noxon Ibraximovna Oripova

Lecturer, Uzbek national institute of Music and Arts, Uzbekistan

Abstract. *This article provides information about the importance of preparation for the lesson in the formation of the teacher's pedagogical skills, and the methodical measures to be taken to prepare for the lesson. Analysis of educational language material Each lesson or group of lessons (paragraph) contains a specific language material. It is not unlikely that the new material will present some degree of difficulty. We determine this by conducting a linguistic unit from the practice of students' language experience.*

Keywords: *brief analysis, student activity, next lesson, independent study, written exercises, reading the text aloud.*

Introduction: Information on methodical measures to be taken to prepare for the lesson: with a deep understanding of the goals of education to determine achievement and lesson goals/tasks; to understand the essence of a modern lesson, that is, to clearly imagine the demands placed on it; analysis of educational language material; finding a sequence (hierarchy) of exercises, i.e. planning ways of building/controlling skills and competences; choosing the equipment used in the lesson; to be able to foresee the educational activities followed by the teacher and the expected behavior of the students in the acquisition of skills and competencies; determining the type of lesson; developing lesson and subject plans.

Let's take a closer look at the noted components of the content of teacher training for a foreign language class. We list the modern requirements for the lesson: the main goal of the lesson is not to explain the rules (abstracts) about a foreign language, but to create skills and competences; speech practice (exercises) imitates the communicative speech process; methodical organization of foreign language material in the lesson is realized as a whole (speech sample is the main unit in all exercises); each type of speech activity is taught using a suitable system of exercises; the lesson will have a single leading goal and auxiliary goals; the effectiveness of the lesson depends on the activity of the students; control in the lesson is in an educational spirit; whenever possible, the lesson is conducted in a foreign language; with the help of the content of the educational material, carefully developed methodical methods and demonstration, students' interest and desire to know is awakened; the lesson is an educational and general educational task, raising the level of students, increasing the desire to know, and contributing to educational work; the age and educational level of the student is taken into account during the lesson; a foreign language lesson is one stage of using certain language material in acquiring speech activity.

Difficulties of a foreign language are taken into account by the author of the textbook when creating exercises. When the teacher prepares for the teaching material of this lesson, he analyzes the comparison of native language and foreign language phenomena. Increases attention to extremely difficult language units and, if necessary, introduces additional exercises.

Material and methods: Difficulties of a foreign language are taken into account by the author of the textbook when creating exercises. When the teacher prepares for the teaching material of this lesson,

he analyzes the comparison of native language and foreign language phenomena. Increases attention to extremely difficult language units and, if necessary, introduces additional exercises. Ensuring the sequence of exercises, taking into account the skills and qualifications of the students, and determining the order of exercises performed in the lesson will give a good result.

With the intention of incorporating the presented and previously learned educational language material into skills and competences, three-stage exercises are recommended - formative, developing and improving. The teacher carefully analyzes the requirements and material of the exercises of the lesson. The most effective method of performing the exercises in the textbook and given by him will be developed. Choosing equipment for the lesson During the preparation for the lesson, special attention is paid to the choice of educational tools. Sufficient and necessary equipment is prepared depending on the purpose of the lesson, new material, exercises and the level of students. The use of technical and simple, educational-methodical complex and hand-made audio-visual tools and methods of their use are thought out. The actions of the teacher and the students are carefully thought out in preparation for the lesson. A teacher should have professional pedagogical skills (planning, research, organization and training), methodical skills (teaching, knowledge of language, knowledge of mastery theory, age and personality characteristics of students).

Having mastered the planning skills, the teacher will be able to choose the language material, interact with the students, and organize the lesson correctly. The educational qualification of the teacher includes the realization of lesson goals/tasks, organization of students' activities for the formation of skills and competences, teaching and supervision of speech communication.

Organizational skills mean implementation of the set plan, organization of students' educational work, use of audio-visual tools, management of students' learning process. Educational tasks include determining the educational and educational purpose of the lesson, attracting additional material, educating students in foreign language material. Knowledge (research) skills include scientific analysis of educational material, observation of students' learning activities, analysis of own and other teachers' work experience. During the preparation for the lesson, the teaching skills of the teacher and the learning skills of the students should be taken into account.

Result and discussion: The lesson, which is the main form of organization of foreign language teaching in higher education institutions, is classified (typology) in different ways. Some teachers based on the purpose of the lesson, some based on the purpose and content of the lesson, and others based on the purpose and topic of the lesson and expressed their opinion about its types. In the scientific literature, when differentiating the types of the lesson, its purpose is taken as the main criterion, and students' independence is taken as an additional criterion. The first criterion is a well-analysed quality in the methodology, and the second (independent activity) takes into account the student's eagerness when working under the guidance of the teacher and in his/her own activities. In the didactic sources, the structure of the lesson, such as asking for homework, explaining and preliminary reinforcement of the educational material, and controlling the acquired knowledge, from the point of view of teaching the basics of science, was highlighted and was once recommended in foreign language teaching. Since the beginning of teaching a foreign language based on the theory of speech activity (psycholinguistics), the one-sided approach in the theory of general education has been abandoned.

Since the 1960s, foreign language lessons have been divided into two types. According to the definition of leading Methodist scientists, the names of pure speech class and mixed speech class appeared. The first type of pure speech class includes lessons devoted to the development of speech skills, based on the speech skills formed on the basis of the learned language material. The essence of these lessons is speech exercises. The activity of the teacher and the student is focused on giving/receiving information based on the topic of the speech, the teacher of mixed speech or the text. An exercise is performed to develop skills in one or more types of speech activity. Less attention is paid to language material. In the second type of mixed speech classes, more exercises are performed on the use of language material. The purpose of the lesson is to develop speech skills and abilities along with mastering lexical, grammatical, and pronunciation material. In such classes, presentation of new material, its application and speech practice are conducted together. A system of exercises

that ensures the unity of language material and speech practice is launched.

A set of lessons (sessions) that serve to form skills and competence on a topic/text or in a specific language material is called a system of lessons. The lesson system covers one and several paragraphs. Based on the overall goal of the system, the goal of a single lesson is determined, it can be mixed speech lessons or other lessons. The term speech lesson itself indicates that the purpose of the lesson is to develop speech skills. Mixed classes include reading and understanding the text, listening comprehension of the audio text, individual and paired lessons. So, depending on the type of speech activity or language material in the educational process, the lesson is conducted in different forms.

Conclusion: Homework of the first category can be done in different ways: repeating the work done in class without changing it, returning it with partial changes, and doing it independently. Independence takes more place in the second homework. The third type of homework is not related to the lesson, so it is done based on the language experience gained by the student. Homework can be given independently of the lesson, but a lesson without homework is rare. At home, mostly written exercises and reading the text aloud are done. Homework is a relatively independent work of students, but it does not completely escape the teacher's control.

References

1. Усубжонова Ш., Орипова Р. УСТОЗЛАР МАКТАБИ. ҚАДИМДА МАВЖУД БЎЛГАН КАСБИЙХУҚУҚИЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАР //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 809-815.
2. ASATULLAYEVA D. G. U. LUG ‘ATLAR SHAKLLANISHI VA ULARNING MAZMUN-SIFATINI ANIQLASH (TERMINOLOGIYA MISOLIDA) //TADQIQOTLAR. UZ. – 2024. – Т. 39. – №. 8. – С. 204-209.
3. Орипова Р. Раъно Орипова. Ўзбек ўлттық классикалық музыкасындағы ўлттық мотивтердің түрлері колорит национальных мотивов в узбекской национальной классической музыке //Журнал. К. – Т. 89.
4. Oripova R. I. Ways to develop the pedagogue's competence in improving the quality of education. StoneDAU //Pedagogy, psychology and teaching methodology.
5. Орипова Р. И. и др. Касбий таълимда фанлааоро алоқадорликни таъминлаш масалалари //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 750-754.
6. Anvarovich Yakubov , O. (2024). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF MEMORIZING MUSICAL TERMS IN PERSIAN. *Oriental Journal of Philology*, 4(03), 382–386. <https://doi.org/10.37547/supsci-ojp-04-03-50>
7. Yakubov O. A. ASSOCIATION METHOD AS A WAY TO IMPLEMENT INNOVATIVE APPROACHES //CUTTING EDGE-SCIENCE. – 2020. – С. 84.
8. Teshaboyeva Ziyodakhon Qodirovna, & Qodiriy Mahzuna Shavkataliyevna. (2024). THE APPEARANCE OF VISUAL EXPRESSIONS’ TRANSLATION INTO ENGLISH IN THE WORK “THE DAYS GONE BY” BY ABDULLA QODIRIY. *Open Access Repository*, 10(1), 78–81. Retrieved from <https://oarepo.org/index.php/oa/article/view/3983>
9. Mamaraimova Dildora Bakhtiyarovna, . (2022). CLASSIFICATION OF DIFFICULTIES IN IMPROVING LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH AMONG STUDENTS OF THE FACULTY OF TOURISM. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(11), 45–48. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/eijmrms/article/view/23288>
10. Mamaraimova Dildor Bakhtiyarovna. (2022). The Specifics of Improving Lexical Competence in Teaching the English Language Course To Students of Tourism Faculties of The Republic of Uzbekistan. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 2(4), 300–302. Retrieved from <https://www.inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/911>

11. Mamaraimova Dildora Baxtiyarovna. Psychological and pedagogical fundamentals of teaching foreign language lexicons for students of the faculty of tourism. *Xorazm Ma'mun Akademiyasi Axborotnomasi* –10/2021. Bet. 415-417
12. Shirnazarova, Z. A. (2023). THE CONCEPT OF “INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION” IN THE CONTEXT OF TODAY’S SOCIETY. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 4(03), 174-179.
13. Nigora Djampulatova. Universitet ta'lim mayonida kouchinglik texnologiyalarini rivojlanish. (2024). *Ta'limning Zamonaviy Transformatsiyasi*, 7(3), 86-93. <https://pedagoglar.org/index.php/03/article/view/2258>
14. Мамараймова Д. Б., Эшмуратова Д. У. МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ГРАММАТИКЕ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В СРЕДНЕМ ЗВЕНЕ ОСНОВНОЙ ШКОЛЫ КАК СРЕДСТВО ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ //Вестник современной науки. – 2016. – №. 3-2. – С. 72-76.
15. Мамараймова Д. Б. ПРИЕМЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА ПО КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ МЕТОДИКЕ //Наука среди нас. – 2018. – №. 6. – С. 347-349.
16. МАМАРАЙМОВА, Д. (2018). РОЛЬ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ШКОЛЕ. *Наука среди нас*, (6), 350-352.